

RESTORING (HEALING) THE *IMAGO DEI*: THE TRANSFORMATIVE POWER OF EVANGELIZATION

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The biblical-theological concept of the human person as created in the image and likeness of God (*imago Dei*) is foundational to the Christian vision of humanity (Gen 1:26–28). It affirms the unique dignity and identity of the human person as bearer of God’s image and sharer in divine attributes, making him capable of communion with God and stewardship over God’s creation. However, this image was profoundly wounded by the disobedience of the first parents (Gen 3), which alienated man from God, self, others and creation itself. God the Creator, in His mercy, responded by initiating a plan of salvation that culminated in the incarnation of Jesus Christ. Christ reconciled humanity to God and opened the path to the restoration of the original dignity and vocation of humanity. Jesus commissioned his disciples and the Church (Lk 24:47; Acts 1:8) to continue his mission of restoring the divine image in humanity by healing the fragmentation caused by sin and reconstituting human beings in their original identity, vocation, and communion.

The evangelizing mission mandated by Christ is not merely the transmission of doctrine for the salvation of individuals, but a participation in the divine project of re-creating humanity in the image of Christ. The *Imago Dei* doctrine provides a profound framework for understanding evangelization as the healing of the humanity wounded by sin. Although the theology of the *imago Dei* was largely neglected by modern western philosophers and theologians, the theme assumed prominence in the post-Vatican II magisterial teaching and theological research. The International Theological Commission (2004) states, “the truth that human beings are created in the image of God is at the heart of Christian revelation.”¹ This foundational vision of man as image-

¹ The International Theological Commission [ITC], *Communion and Stewardship: Human Persons Created in the Image of God* (2004), 1 [hereafter CS].

bearers of God has deep implications for Christian life and mission in response to the challenges posed by scientific and philosophical advances to human dignity.² Rooted in the Scriptures, the Church Fathers, and centuries of theological reflection on the *Imago Dei*, we can confidently affirm that evangelization is a healing and transformative process of restoring humanity's relational, rational, and spiritual capacities, aligning them with Christ, the perfect image of God. This article seeks to propose 'the restoration of *imago Dei*' as a vital framework for a missiology that is capable of answering the contemporary anthropological and existential questions facing contemporary humanity (Cf. CS 1). The biblical-patristic-theological vision of Christ as the healer of the *imago Dei* emerges as a counter-cultural narrative vis-à-vis the anthropological and cultural crises of the 21st century.

1. CREATED IN THE IMAGE AND LIKENESS OF GOD

The doctrine of humanity's creation in the image and likeness of God is rooted in Genesis 1:26–27, which reads: “Let us make man in our image, after our likeness” (Gen 1:26); the same is reaffirmed in the subsequent verse, “So God created man in his own image, in the image of God he created him; male and female he created them” (Gen 1:27, RSV). The Hebrew *tselem* (image) implies a representation or reflection, while *demut* (likeness) suggests resemblance. Together they indicate that humans are created with divine attributes such as dominion and stewardship over creation (Gen 1:28), rationality and moral freedom (Wis 2:23; Sir 17:1–3), along with capacity for relationship with God and one another (Gen 2:15–17; Ps 8). This endows each human person with a rational, moral, and spiritual capacity that mirrors God's relational being and distinguishes humans from the rest of creation. The New Testament identifies Christ as “the image of the invisible God” (Col 1:15; cf. 2 Cor 4:4), calling humanity to be “conformed to the image of his Son” through grace (Rom 8:29; cf. Eph 4:24; Col 3:10). Ultimately, the image of God in man is understood as ‘sonship in the Son’ and spiritual resemblance to God (Luke 3:38; cf. Eph 4:24; Col 3:10).

² The ITC document *Communion and Stewardship* “reaffirms the truth that human persons are created in the image of God in order to enjoy personal communion [with Trinity] . . . , and in order to exercise, in God's name, responsible stewardship of the created world” (CS 4).

Theologically, the *imago Dei* shaped Christian anthropology and firmly established human dignity and moral responsibility, underpinning ethical principles like justice and love. While the terms “image” and “likeness” appear together, their exact distinction remains debated, leading to nuanced interpretations. Irenaeus of Lyons (c. 130–202) distinguished between “image” and “likeness” and argued that the “image” refers to humanity’s inherent endowments of reason, free will, and immortality, possessed from the beginning and retained even after the Fall, while “likeness”, the moral and spiritual resemblance to God, was lost or diminished through sin³. According to Gregory of Nyssa (c. 335–395), the image is not a static attribute but a dynamic potential for *theosis* (divinization) or the capacity to become like God through exercise of freedom through virtuous choices⁴, a process hindered by sin yet enabled by Christ’s redemptive work.

Augustine (354–430) located the image in the soul’s Trinitarian faculties of memory, understanding, and will, and displayed in the mind’s capacity to remember, understand, and love, reflecting God’s triune nature. Thomas Aquinas (1225–1274) taught that the *image* resides in the rational faculties of intellect and will, while *likeness* (*similitudo*) refers to supernatural grace and charity, diminished by original sin⁵ but restorable through the Spirit. All Fathers, including Augustine and theologian Thomas, agree that the image, though obscured by sin, denotes a dynamic process of spiritual growth toward divine perfection, fully realized through Christ and to be acquired by man through the Holy Spirit.

Contemporary theologians and popes, building on patristic foundations, demonstrate a predilection to view humanity’s creation in God’s image within a Christocentric and Trinitarian framework. *Gaudium et Spes* of Vatican II highlights Christ as “the image of the invisible God” (Col 1:15) and declares, “The truth is that only in the mystery of the incarnate Word does the mystery of man take on light... Christ... fully reveals man to himself and makes his supreme calling clear” (GS 22; cf. also GS12, 24). Karl Rahner interprets the *imago*

³ Irenaeus, *Against Heresies*, trans. A. Roberts & J. Donaldson, 1885, Book V, 6.1.

⁴ Gregory of Nyssa, *On the Making of Man*, trans. P. Schaff & H. Wace, 1892.

⁵ Augustine, *On the Trinity*, trans. E. Hill, 1991, Book XIV, 8.11; St. Thomas, *Summa Theologiae*, I, Q. 93, Art. 4.

Dei as humanity's inherent transcendental openness to divine self-communication: "Man is not merely a being who has the image of God; he is this image insofar as his spiritual existence is constituted by an orientation toward the absolute mystery, we call God."⁶ John Paul II, in *Redemptor Hominis* (1979), affirms, "he [Man]... remains a being that is incomprehensible for himself, if he does not encounter love This ... is why Christ the Redeemer 'fully reveals man to himself' (RH10). He argues that "Created in the divine image and likeness, the human person ... is 'capax Dei', capable of knowing God and of receiving the gift he makes of himself."⁷

Ratzinger develops a "*theological humanism*" rooted in divine sonship shared by humans through the incarnation of Christ, the "*true image of God*" (Col 1:15) to critique the modern secular anthropologies that reduce the person to mere biological or economic functions. Orthodox theologian David Bentley Hart too challenges the secular anthropologies that deny the metaphysical uniqueness of human beings and articulates the concept of the image of God in humanity: "The human longing ... our innate and unremitting orientation toward the infinite—that makes us who we are."⁸ Gustavo Gutiérrez, the pioneer of liberation theology, reinterprets the *Imago Dei* in light of social justice and human dignity. Some neuroscientists too cite *Imago Dei* concept to describe higher cognitive functions in humans: "The image of God is reflected in our embodied capacities for higher cognitive functions ... which emerge from the dynamic complexity of the human brain but point to a relational and purposeful orientation toward God."⁹ Thus we can see that the *imago Dei* remains a dynamic

⁶ Karl Rahner, "Theological Anthropology," in *Sacramentum Mundi: An Encyclopedia of Theology*, vol. 1 (New York: Herder and Herder, 1968), 335–345; restated in K. Rahner, *Foundations of Christian Faith: An Introduction to the Idea of Christianity*, trans. William V. Dych (New York: Seabury, 1978), 114–122

⁷ https://www.vatican.va/content/john-paul-ii/en/audiences/1998/documents/hf_jp-ii_aud_26081998.html

⁸ David Bentley Hart, *The Experience of God: Being, Consciousness, Bliss* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2013) 292, (paraphrased).

⁹ Warren S. Brown, "Cognitive Contributions to Soul" in *Whatever Happened to the Soul? Scientific and Theological Portraits of Human Nature*, edited by Warren S. Brown, N. Murphy, and H. Newton Maloney (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 1998) 99–125, here 102.

and unifying doctrine in Catholic theology, challenging all reductionist views of the person and affirming humanity's divine calling.

2. WOUNDED BY SIN AND IN NEED OF HEALING

Having explored the *imago Dei* as the cornerstone of Christian anthropology, we now turn to the biblical reality that sin has profoundly wounded this divine image in man. The Fall of Adam and Eve (Gen 3) portrays *sin* as a disruption of human communion with God, rendering humanity vulnerable to suffering, death. The 'original sin' inclined humans toward selfishness and rebellion, with the devastating impact of obscuring the relational and moral dimensions of the *imago Dei*, leaving behind a fractured relationships with God, one another, and creation. This idea is reinforced in Genesis 5:1-3 and 9:1-7, emphasizing multiplication of sin post-fall, with Genesis 6:5 suggesting that 'every imagination of the thoughts of human heart was only evil continually'. Although Gen 9:6 affirms the retention of the image despite sin,¹⁰ the serious wounding of human nature is apparent in the broken communion with God, others, and creation, discernible in the pages of the Bible.

Theological opinions vary on the effect of sin on the image and likeness, mostly dictated by the understanding of image and likeness itself. Yet Fathers of the Church in general agree that original sin, inherited from the disobedience of Adam and Eve (Gen 3; Rom 5:12–19), has obscured, weakened, or wounded the divine image in man, especially, its relational and moral dimensions, but has not erased it. Irenaeus, who distinguishes between image (the created nature) and likeness (the gift of the Spirit), portrays the Fall as a rupture of relationship and the sin as an "ancient wound" inflicted by Satan. Irenaeus, who emphasizes that while image is retained, man lost the *likeness* or the "robe of sanctity" bestowed by the Spirit and man stands in need of restoration through Christ.¹¹

Gregory of Nyssa too describes sin as a "defacement" of the divine image, where humanity's freedom, meant for virtue, is misused, leading to estrangement from God. But Christ came to help humans to fully

¹⁰ "Whoever sheds the blood of a human, by a human shall that person's blood be shed, for God made man in his own image" (Gen 9:6).

¹¹ Irenaeus, *Against Heresies*, Book III, 23.5; *On the Making of Man*, 12.9.

realize the latent capacity to grow into likeness to God. Augustine notes that sin darkens the soul's capacity to reflect God's glory and obscures the soul's capacity to remember, understand, and love God fully, making grace necessary for renewal.¹² "Created after the image of God ... it [humanity] lost righteousness and true holiness by sinning, through which that image became defaced and tarnished; and this it recovers when it is formed again and renewed ... [by Christ]."¹³ Aquinas, similarly, argued that the natural faculties of the *image* endure, but the supernatural *likeness* is forfeited, leaving humanity estranged from God and disordered in relationships.

The current Catholic thinking on *imago Dei* is synthesised in the *Catechism of the Catholic Church*: "Man, enticed by the evil one, abused his freedom. He still bore the image of God, but was deprived of the original likeness" (CCC 705). Despite sin, "the divine image is present in every man" (CCC 1702) and for this reason, every human life, even in its most vulnerable state, possesses inalienable dignity because it reflects the Creator. The ITC document *Communion and Stewardship*, similarly, clarifies that sin 'disfigures' the *imago Dei*, though it does not obliterate it: "Catholic tradition has always insisted that, while the *Imago Dei* is impaired or disfigured, it cannot be destroyed by sin ... grace and salvation... transform the existing, albeit sinful, reality of human nature" (CS 46). Sin as a rupture of the relationship with God, wounds the divine image without annihilating it and "man... remains capable of receiving the saving divine activity" (CS 45, 46).

The above analysis shows that Catholic thought is unanimous that humans retain their unique status as God's image even after sin, while the moral and spiritual alignment with God is stained. The Reformation tradition is not radically different¹⁴, although some later protestant

¹² Augustine, *On the Literal Meaning of Genesis*, Book VI, 27, trans. J.H. Taylor, 1982.

¹³ St. Augustine, *On the Trinity*, XIV.17.

¹⁴ Reformation thinkers, such as John Calvin and Martin Luther, hold strongly the loss or severe distortion of the image through sin, but emphasized its restoration through Christ (Calvin, *Institutes of the Christian Religion*, I.15.4). Karl Barth in *Church Dogmatics*, III/1, interpreted the *imago Dei* relationally, arguing that it is fulfilled in human community and covenant with God, reflecting the relational nature of the Trinity. According to Moltmann, the image is

traditions diverge. The truth is that despite sin's distortion, the *imago Dei* remains ontologically intact and allows for redemption through Christ's incarnation and redemption. Even sinners retain the *image* and the capacity for *likeness* and, hence, stand in need of redemption through Christ. Christ, as the perfect image, restores humanity's capacity to reflect divine glory. Tradition affirms that human nature remains transformable, albeit sinful reality of human nature through evangelization.

3. THE IMAGE RESTORED BY INCARNATION

All Christian traditions -Catholic, Orthodox and Reformed- affirm that Christ is the true image of God and, in union with Him, the human person is fully restored. Patristic testimonies abound on this point. Irenaeus of Lyons, who framed the Fall as a loss of likeness, hold that the image remained to be healed only through incarnate Christ: "Men cannot be saved in any other way from the ancient wound of the Serpent except by believing in Him... who... drew all things to Himself and gave life to the dead."¹⁵ His logic is that "the ancient wound" inflicted by Satan is undone through Christ's redeeming wounds and man was restored to the original image by the incarnate Son, who is the [true] image of God. Athanasius taught that Christ took mortal flesh to serve as the healing cure for human corruption introduced by Adam's fall.¹⁶ He asks, "What, then, was God to do? ... renew His Image in mankind? ... And how could this be done save by the coming of the very Image Himself, our Saviour Jesus Christ? ... He assumed a human body, in order that in it ... men might be renewed according to the Image."¹⁷ With

not a static attribute but a dynamic calling to live in communion, expressed through embodiment and interdependence. Moltmann notes that the wound of sin manifests in broken community, ecological exploitation, and estrangement from God's Spirit. Jürgen Moltmann, *God in Creation: A New Theology of Creation and the Spirit of God* (San Francisco: Harper & Row, 1985), 223.

¹⁵ Irenaeus, *Against Heresies* 4.2.8. See also, "Just as the human race was bound to death by a virgin, it is released through a virgin... the wisdom of the Serpent was conquered... and we were released from the chains by which we were bound to death" *Against Heresies* 5.19.

¹⁶ Athanasius, *On the Incarnation* 2:9; 4:20–21.

¹⁷ Athanasius, *On the Incarnation* 3:13.

the ancient formula, “*God became man so that man might become god*”¹⁸ Gregory Nazianzus too underscores that Christ assumed fallen human nature so as to heal its wound. Augustine supports the view stating “That image may begin to be formed again by Him by whom it had been formed at first. ... That image cannot form itself again, as it could deform itself ... and this it recovers when it is formed again and renewed.”¹⁹ Thus the Patristic testimony is rife with statements that though fallen, humanity retains its capacity to reflect Christ, who restored humanity to original condition. This Patristic vision is firmly rooted in the biblical witness.

3.1 The Biblical vision of Restoration through Christ

The Bible tells the story of the progressive attempt of God to restore and reinstate the fallen man into the original condition. Old Testament provides glimpses of God’s restorative work through covenants, laws, and prophetic call to justice and righteousness. The Exodus event and the provisions in the Mosaic Law reveal God’s care and concern for those whose *imago Dei* is diminished by oppression. Finally, the promise of redemption in Gen 3:15 is actualised in the New Testament, which reveals the fullness of God’s restorative work in the incarnation of Jesus Christ. Jesus, as “the Word made flesh,” communicates God’s truth and grace, offering redemption and reconciliation, which marks the final and full restoration of humanity into the image of the only begotten Son. Jesus’s ministry of healing—physical, spiritual, and emotional—demonstrates God’s desire to restore humans to wholeness, which is continued by the Church to the ends of the earth and the ends of time.

Of the New Testament writings, Johannine and Pauline theologies of redemption brings to light the anthropological implications of redemption stated as restoration of the original dignity as children of God through Christ.

3.2 Johannine idea of Restoration of the Image of God

According to John, Jesus, the ‘Incarnate Logos’ (Jn 1:14) is the only begotten Son of God, who was with the Father from the

¹⁸ St. Gregory of Nazianzus, *Letter to Cledonius* (Letter 101).

¹⁹ St. Augustine, *De Trinitate*, Book XV: Chapter 16, Section 22.

beginning of creation (Jn 1:1-2) and has become human to provide him with a new identity (Jn 3:16). Jesus told Nicodemus that “One must be reborn ... to enter the Kingdom of God” (Jn 3:3). Reading it together with the Prologue brings out the anthropological framework for understanding the relation between redemption and the restoration of the image of God in man. By rebirth through water and Spirit, Jesus means the restoration of the original identity and dignity of man to be bestowed by the incarnate Logos: “... to all who received him, who believed in his name, he gave them power to become children of God” (John 1:12). By new birth believers are invited to a new relationship with God as children of God and are given a new identity in Christ as sons in the Son.

This includes both personal and communal transformation of humanity and a renewal of the entire creation. According to John, Jesus Christ has come to lead people from darkness (ignorance and sin) to light (Truth and Life), offering them a new identity and dignity (Jn 1:5; 3:19; 14:9). He promises “life in abundance” (Jn 10:10) reminiscent of the paradisiac life. The Risen Christ revealed his original nature and identity to the disciples and empowered them by the Spirit and sent them forth as witnesses of redeemed life in Jesus: “As the Father has sent me, so I send you” (Jn 20:21-23). John concludes the Gospel with the same missionary intent: “These are written so that you may believe that Jesus is the Christ, the Son of God, and that by believing you may have life in His name” (John 20:31)²⁰.

3.3 Pauline theology of Restoration of Image

Paul’s writings further illuminate the anthropological dimension of redemption and provide deeper understanding of the restoration process through evangelization. Like in John, the idea of rebirth is at the centre of Pauline narrative: “... if anyone is in Christ, there is a

²⁰ John does not narrate stories of Jesus sending the disciples out to preach and heal like in Synoptics (cf. Mt 10:1-42; Mk 6:1-6; Lk 9:1-6; 10:1-20). Mission in John is the activity of the triune God, wherein Father’s love moves to send the Son (Jn 20:21) and the Spirit for the salvation of the world. Jesus sends the disciples: “As the Father has sent me, I am sending you” (John 20:21b). The disciples are witnesses of Jesus (15:26-27), through whose lives transformed by relationship to Jesus and his sending (Jn 15:1-16) that “the world will come to know” Jesus (Jn 17:21).

new creation” (2Cor 5:17-18), thanks to the ministry of reconciliation by Christ. Paul explains it further in Romans, in terms of death to sinful old ways and resurrection to new life: those who believe in Christ and are baptised have ‘died to sin’ and ‘raised with Christ’ to “walk in the newness of life” (Rom 6:3-4). Their ‘old self is crucified with him’ and ‘sinful body is destroyed and are ‘no longer enslaved to sin’ and ‘death has no longer any dominion over them’ (Rom 6:6-10), who are “dead to sin and alive to God in Jesus Christ” (Rom 6:11). This is the law of grace (Gospel), that “you who were once slaves of sin have become obedient from the heart to the standard of teaching to which you were committed” to ‘righteousness and sanctification’ (Rom 6: 17-19).

For Paul, Jesus Christ is “the image of the invisible God” (Col 1:15), “the first-born of all creation” (means, the archetypal image) and “in him all the fulness of God” (v.19) dwells and he has ‘reconciled (redeemed) to himself all things’ ‘making peace by the blood of his cross” (Col 1:15-20). What Paul means is that through faith in Christ, a progressive restoration of humanity to the original image is taking place, transforming all those who believe in him into the image of God” (2Cor 3:18). The reconciliation and transformation of humanity happens through “the light of the gospel of the glory of Christ, who is the image of God” (2Cor 4:4).

Again, for Paul, redemption means “to be conformed to the image of his Son” (Rom 8:29): “the Spirit himself bearing witness with our spirit that we are children of God” (v.16), worthy to address God as “Abba! Father!” (v.15) and as “children, ... heirs of God” (v.17). So, who has received the Gospel is “no longer slave (to sin), “but a son” (Rom 8:15-17; Gal 4:6-7). What Paul means is not only a moral and behavioural change (individual conversion), but also ontological transformation of individuals and communities from the fallen state of sin to restoration of the original identity and dignity through the salvific action of Christ the Image and the sanctifying power of the Holy Spirit. This is the Gospel to be proclaimed.

3.4 The Pauline Vision of the Scope of Evangelization

In Ephesians chapter 4, Paul describes God’s grand plan to restore the original ‘image and likeness of God.’ Paul speaks of a deep transformation at the heart of Christian life: the replacement

of the old humanity (*palaios anthrōpos*), corrupted by sin, with the new humanity (*kainos anthrōpos*) re-created in Christ (cf. Eph 4:22-24; Col 3:9-10). Through the ministry of the Word (evangelization), Paul hopes to bring about “the mature manhood ... to the measure of the stature of the fulness of Christ” (Eph 4: 11-13). He believes that humanity can be liberated from the corruption of minds, darkness of understanding, ignorance of truth, slavery to licentiousness, and every kind of uncleanness” (Eph 4:18-24): “Put off your old nature which belongs to your former manner of life and is corrupt through deceitful lusts, and be renewed in the spirit of your minds, and put on the new nature, created after the likeness of God in true righteousness and holiness” (Eph 4: 22-24). This is not a mere moral upgrade, but a radical reconstitution of what it means to be truly human again, to be reoriented toward truth, justice, and holiness (Ephesians 4:20–24).

The Pauline concept of ‘being in Christ’ underlines a restored identity which transcends socio-economic and cultural barriers. The proclamation of the Gospel leads also to a reunification of scattered humanity into “one new humanity” in the “bond of peace” – Shalom, the original plan of creation – (Cf. Eph 2:14-16): “There is one body and one Spirit, just as you were called to the one hope that belongs to your call, one Lord, one faith, one baptism, one God and Father of us all” (Eph 4: 4-6). Hence his idea of ‘mystical body of Christ’ (Cf. 1 Cor 12:12-31; Col 1:18; 2:18-20; Eph. 1:22-23; 3:19; 4:13), is not a mere metaphor of interdependence but a cosmic vision of a community that values and defends the image of each individual and reinforces the communitarian existence of man and his dignity within the created cosmos.

The Gospel transformation affects the entire creation and involves the defeat of alienation of sin and the restoration of the original unity within self, with God, with others and the creation. In this way, evangelization is nothing less than a participation in God’s act of new creation. Paul evangelized with urgency - “woe to me if I do not preach” – because, “the whole creation has been groaning in labour pains until now” and through Christ “the creation itself will be set free from its bondage to decay and will obtain the freedom of the glory of the children of God” even as the human beings are the ‘first fruits of the Spirit’ (Rom 8:21-23). Only Christ restores and elevates human nature, making believers conformed again to the image of the Son

(cf. Rom 8:29). “The image of God is renewed in the life of grace, perfected in glory” (CCC 1701–1709) through Christ, the “image of the invisible God” (Col 1:15). It means that evangelizing mission is intrinsically linked to the state of man in this world, along with all problems and prospects of the humankind. It is this anthropological truth that necessitates evangelization, which is the divine invitation to a new form of existence—a humanity animated by the Spirit, configured to Christ, and integrated in body, mind, and heart (cf. 2 Cor 5:17).

4. RESTORATION OF *IMAGO DEI*: AN ANTHROPOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR MISSION

The Johannine and Pauline theologies of ‘new birth’ and ‘new being’ in Christ provide us with a solid anthropological framework for mission from the perspective of *imago Dei*. While the Johannine concept of being ‘born again’ encapsulates the transformative process of accepting and internalizing the teaching of Christ (evangelization), Pauline theology of ‘new creation’ in Christ emphasizes the potential restoration of humans and creation from the fallen state of sin, through the passion, death and resurrection of Christ. Such a renovation of humanity is not merely an eschatological goal, but a current reality and experience. Evangelization is an ‘already not yet’ phenomenon, in the Synoptic sense, whereby the renewal begins here and now and anticipates complete restoration in the eschatological time. Through evangelization, humans are invited to move from the fallen state of humanity to renewed state through belief in Christ. The Gospel offers hope and power to humans to work for holistic social restoration in the light of the revealed redeeming work of Christ.

The unprecedented challenges and opportunities emerging from technological advancements, communication revolution, globalisation and migration, necessitate a robust mission theology that reinterprets the message of salvation to affirm the wealth of human diversity and the transformative power of the Gospel. And, the conviction that humanity is restored to *imago Dei* through Christ remains the ontological foundation of human dignity and provides a robust foundation for a theology of mission for our times. The idea of re-aligning of humanity with its divine purpose constitutes the theological bedrock of evangelization today. The ‘new birth’ of humanity through restoration of the divine image involves spiritual-bodily renewal as well as social, cultural and cosmic healing of creation.

4.1 Spiritual and Bodily Renewal through Evangelization

Evangelization is not merely a transfer of beliefs, but a call for transformation of individuals and communities. God's creative act was holistic (Gen. 2:7) and Christ's saving work embraces the whole person, redeeming both the spiritual faculties (mind, will, soul) and the bodily existence that shares in the hope of resurrection (1 Cor. 15:42–44). Paul exhorts believers to “*be renewed in the spirit of your minds, and put on the new self, created after the likeness of God*” (Eph 4:23-24) present their bodies as ‘a living sacrifice’ (Romans 12:1-2, 1 Cor 6:20; 2 Cor 4:6). The restoration of the *imago Dei* is not purely spiritual; it heals humanity in its totality, body, mind and spirit. The Patristic linking of the *imago Dei* to deification (*theosis*) goes a step further to refer to spiritual participation of man in divine nature through grace (2 Peter 1:4) assigns pride of place to evangelization and sacramental life in the restoration of man.²¹ The words of Irenaeus that “the glory of God is the human being fully alive”,²² underscores the vivification of the whole person as the goal of redemption.²³ Among modern theologians, Balthasar expressed it best: “Man is most himself when he is conformed to Christ the perfect Image who reveals the Father’s glory.”²⁴ Mission, thus, effects “the radical liberation of the human person through grace” (RM58), through personal transformation and forming habits, virtues and values of the kingdom.

4.2 The Church as the Visible Sign of Restored Humanity

Biblical vision of salvation is not just about individual salvation but deeply communal. Mission is intrinsically ecclesial: evangelization incorporates persons into a community whose reconciled diversity manifests the renewed *imago* (Eph 4:1–6). Paul envisages all things in heaven and earth united in the Messiah, in whom the barriers that

²¹ See M. C. Steenberg, *Of God and Man: Theology as Anthropology from Irenaeus to Athanasius*, T & T Clarke, New York, 2009, 29-34.

²² Irenaeus, *Against Heresies*, 4.20.7, in Alexander Roberts and James Donaldson eds., *Ante-Nicene Fathers*, vol. 1 (Peabody, MA: Hendrickson, 1994), 490.

²³ Eph 1:10; Irenaeus, *Against Heresies*, 3.16.6; V.21.1. *Catechism of the Catholic Church* teaches that in Christ “the divine image, disfigured in man by the first sin, has been restored to its original beauty” (CCC 1701).

²⁴ Hans Urs von Balthasar, *The Glory of the Lord: A Theological Aesthetics*, vol. VII: Theology: The New Covenant, trans. Brian McNeil (San Francisco: Ignatius Press, 1989), 124.

once divided humanity—Jew and Gentile, male and female, slave and free—are overcome in a new unity (cf. Gal 3:28; Eph 2:14-16; 1 Pet 2:9–10). The Church, as the Body of Christ (1 Cor 12:27), makes the healed *imago Dei* visible through unity and holiness. In the unity of diverse peoples within the Church we see the undoing of humanity’s ancient divisions. Irenaeus links recapitulation with the gathering of divided humanity in the Body of Christ and Augustine describes the Church as “the world reconciled,”²⁵ reflecting Trinitarian communion. Vatican II affirms that the Church is “in Christ, like a sacrament or as a sign and instrument both of a very closely knit union with God and of the unity of the whole human race” (LG 1, 48). This sacramental identity means that the Church is both the bearer and the locus of the renewed humanity. And evangelization is an invitation to enter into the reconciled community of the Church, the visible assembly of the restored *imago Dei*.

4.3 Renewal of cultures

The Catholicity of the Church refers to the gathering of renewed humanity that includes all nations, cultures and ethnicities. Along with restoring humans, Gospel heals and elevates social and cultural systems “wounded” by sin as well, purifying what is fallen and bringing to fulfilment what is true and good (Ps 96; Acts 17:22–31; Rev 21:24–26). *Gaudium et Spes* 58 affirms that the Gospel heals and elevates cultures: “The good news of Christ continually renews the life and culture of fallen man; it combats and removes the error and evil which flow from the ever-present attraction of sin. It never ceases to purify and elevate the morality of peoples.”²⁶ Pope Paul VI taught that evangelization must penetrate cultures “from within, transforming and renewing them” (EN 18-20) and John Paul II stated emphatically that evangelization renews and transforms the criteria of judgment, values, and customs of people (RM 52). Pope Francis

²⁵ Irenaeus, *Against Heresies*, 3.18.1; 5.14. Augustine, *Expositions of the Psalms* 73–98, (Psalm 95[96], Sermon 2.7) *The Works of Saint Augustine* III/18 (Hyde Park, NY: New City Press, 2002), 451.

²⁶ In similar tone, *Nostra Aetate* 2, *Ad Gentes* 11 and 22 and *Lumen Gentium* 13 affirm that the Gospel not only rejects nothing that is true and holy in cultures and religions but also purifies and elevates them, bringing to fulfilment what is good.

too insists that evangelization must touch the roots of culture and lifestyle: “The Holy Spirit enriches [culture] with the transforming power of the Gospel” (EG 116); “faith must be inculturated and culture must be evangelized” (General Audience, Oct. 2023; cf. EG 117; cf. also 176-77). Evangelization serves to qualify cultures to participate in the “new heavens and new earth” (Rev. 21:1). In the words of Catholic missiologist Stephen Bevans mission must address distorted cultural narratives, embodying the Gospel as “a counter-cultural and transformative force” that restores authentic humanity.²⁷

4.4 Healing of Creation and Integral Ecology

In the biblical vision, humanity’s fall not only wounded human nature but subjected creation itself to “bondage to decay” (Rom. 8:20–21). The healing of the *imago* or the restoration of humanity in Christ therefore inaugurates the restoration of creation as well. While Irenaeus’ doctrine of recapitulation in Christ emphasizes the cosmic scope of redemption, Maximus the Confessor deepens this vision by teaching that all the *logoi* of creation are gathered into the one *Logos*. For Maximus, Christ unites and transfigures the created orders, healing their divisions and redeeming matter itself.²⁸ This is in total congruence with the biblical teaching that ‘creation groans for the revealing of the children of God’ (Rom 8:19–23) and that Christ reconciles “all things” (Col 1:15-20) in order to bring about a new earth and a new heaven (Rev 21-22). Francis’ linking of the creation’s destiny and ecological conversion (LS 66, 83, 217) can be understood as exercising wise dominion or ecological stewardship (Gen 1:28) as originally envisaged at the creation of man in the *imago Dei*. Evangelization that heals the *imago Dei* also renews humanity’s original role in Eden, of guardianship, cultivation, and communion with all creatures. The cosmic scope of mission includes healing of the anthropocentric exploitation of creation promoted by consumerist culture.

4.5 Evangelization as the Filling of the World with God’s Glory

The above points lead us to the understanding that the final horizon of mission is the restoration (*theosis*) of man and creation

²⁷ Stephen B. Bevans and Roger P. Schroeder, *Constants in Context: A Theology of Mission for Today* (Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 2004), 390.

²⁸ Irenaeus, *Against Heresies* 3.16.6); Maximus, *Ambigua* 7; 41.

in the risen and glorified Christ (1 Cor 15:28). The eschatological vision found in Isaiah 11:9 and Habakkuk 2:14 that “the earth shall be full of the knowledge of the Lord as the waters cover the sea” is about the redeemed humanity living out its renewed image, radiating God’s glory in personal holiness, cultural transformation, and cosmic harmony. This happens when Christ’s light, shining in human hearts and communities, penetrates every darkness, drawing all things into His eternal Kingdom through the mission of the Church (2 Cor 4:6; Eph 3:14–19; Matt 5:14–16). Gregory of Nyssa describes the restored image as an ever-deepening participation in God’s infinite beauty, where humanity grows “from glory to glory” (2 Cor. 3:18).²⁹ Balthasar describes Christ’s Passion as theophany, “the Cross is the prism through which God’s glory refracts into the world’s darkness”³⁰ and goes on to say that “mission is nothing less than the drama of God’s glory filling the cosmos, the final act in which the scattered fragments of the divine image are gathered into the unity of Christ’s Body, and the world becomes what it was always meant to be: a liturgy of praise.”³¹ Evangelization is the means by which this divine light spreads into the world. Through the witness of believers, the darkness of sin and ignorance is pushed back, and the earth is increasingly filled with the radiance of God’s truth and love.

5. RESTORATION OF THE *IMAGO DEI* AS A COUNTER-CULTURAL NARRATIVE

This above detailed comprehensive understanding of the multi-faceted restoration of *Imago Dei* as the anthropological framework for mission urges us to take a fresh look at evangelization as a counter-cultural narrative to the dominant ‘post-everything’ cultural scenario of the day. In the contemporary cultural climate, dominated by secular anthropologies, the Christian vision of man created and restored in the image of God can serve as a critical vehicle for navigating the intricacies of the post-modern and New Age relativism, fragmentation, self-redemption spiritualities, and dehumanizing social forces.

²⁹ Gregory of Nyssa, *The Life of Moses*, 2.239–240, trans. Abraham J. Malherbe and Everett Ferguson (New York: Paulist Press, 1978) 115–116.

³⁰ Hans Urs von Balthasar, *Theo-Drama: Theological Dramatic Theory*, vol. IV: The Action (San Francisco: Ignatius Press, 1994), 331.

³¹ Hans Urs von Balthasar, *Theo-Drama: Theological Dramatic Theory*, Vol. V: The Last Act, 511.

5.1 Reminder of the true Identity of Man

Despite the scepticism towards meta-narratives and disconnection from the sacred narratives, the unified biblical vision of man and cosmos serves as an alternative story of God and man by offering man an ‘identity’ and vocation (*imago Dei*) gifted by the Creator (Gen 1:26–28) and renewed by the redeemer ‘according to the Image’ (2 Cor 5:17; Eph 4:22–24 *kainos anthrōpos*). The prevailing ideologies of post-modernity and New Age thoughts often blur the distinction between Creator and creature, and reduce human dignity to self-defined identity constructs. As *Gaudium et Spes* asserts “only in the mystery of the incarnate Word does the mystery of man take on light” and only Christ “fully reveals man to himself and makes his supreme calling clear” (GS 22; Cf. also RH 10). David Bentley Hart critiques secular anthropologies that reduce the human to “a mere biological accident” and affirms that the human person is a *theophany*—a manifestation of divine love and freedom—thus making the restoration of the *imago Dei* not optional but essential to human flourishing.³² Evangelization announces not only a lifestyle option but also proclaims the inherent worth of every person, restoring hope by reconnecting human identity to divine origin and destiny. Mission, when framed as the restoration of the *imago Dei*, “offer a new synthesis capable of illuminating the profound dignity of every human person” (EG 121).

5.2 Alternative to Individualism and Relativism

The emergence of digital communication and social media have transformed the idea of human interaction and community from interpersonal connection to technological interconnectivity, with the inherent risk of fragmentary attention, superficial engagement and extreme individualism. The hyper-technologized social media and digital sphere provide ‘transactional connection’ without mutual encounter at personal level. The Christian vision of the *imago Dei* defines humanity as intrinsically relational, mirroring the Trinitarian communion. The restored image finds its fulfilment in communion (*koinonia*) with God and others (cf. John 17:21), rather than in isolated self-definition (Acts 2:42–47). Mission calls persons to authentic

³² David Bentley Hart, *The Experience of God*, 234.

connection within communities after the model of Trinity and Church, offering a humane alternative to extreme individualism, through the Gospel mantra of truth-in-love and freedom. Evangelization strategies should intentionally seek ways to thwart tendencies of isolation and facilitate deeper connection and global communion using the same globalization and interconnectivity.

5.3 Remedy to Post-Modern Anxiety

Even as the recovery of the *imago Dei* restores relational capacity by incorporating persons into a reconciled body, faith in the renewal of humanity in Christ helps overcome contemporary existential anxiety (meaninglessness, loneliness, despair) characteristic of post-modern culture. Christ promises “life in abundance” (John 10:10), “hope that does not disappoint” (Rom. 8:24), creation’s liberation from futility (Rom. 8:18–25) and a light that sustains believers amid suffering by anticipating “the glory that is to be revealed” through “the knowledge of the glory of God in the face of Jesus Christ” (2 Cor. 4:6). The Magisterium deepens this biblical vision. Pope Francis, in *Christus vivit*³³ identifies Christ and the Church as the antidote to modern despair, announcing human life to be meaningful, purposeful, and destined for communion with God (CV 115–133) and one another. *Evangelii Gaudium* reminds that the Gospel “fills the heart and the whole life of those who encounter Jesus,”³⁴ transforming despair into hope (EG 7–10, 268–274). Pope Benedict XVI adds that “Only when the future is certain as a positive reality does it become possible to live the present as well.”³⁵ Theologically, David Bentley Hart explains that human longing is ultimately metaphysical, seeking fulfillment not in immanent cultural techniques of distraction or self-construction, but in the transcendent Good revealed in Christ, who restores the divine image.³⁶ Christ-centered renewal through evangelization can offer hope, dignity, and authentic joy amid pervasive cultural anxieties.

³³ Francis, *Christus Vivit* [Christ Is Alive!] (Vatican City: Libreria Editrice Vaticana, 2019) §§115–33.

³⁴ Francis, *Evangelii Gaudium* (Vatican City: Libreria Editrice Vaticana, 2013) 8.

³⁵ Benedict XVI, *Spe Salvi* [Saved in Hope] (Vatican City: Libreria Editrice Vaticana, 2007), §2.

³⁶ B. Hart, *Experience of God*, 2–3.

5.4 Antidote to Terrorism, Conflict, and Fragmentation

The restored *imago Dei* calls for the recognition of every human being as a brother or sister making universal fraternity possible and sustainable. The inherently relational and communitarian nature of the triune God widens the horizon of love from family or nation to the global human family, rejecting assimilation and fragmentation. St. Paul is emphatic that Christ our peace breaks down the dividing walls (Eph 2:14–16; Col 3:10–11) through ministry of reconciliation (Gal 3:28; 2 Cor 5:18–20) that “*there is neither Jew nor Greek, slave nor free, male nor female, for you are all one in Christ*” (Gal 3:28), relativising ethnic identities and tribal division, while honouring cultural diversity. *Lumen Gentium* rightly points to “the universal mission” of the Church to be “a sacrament or as a sign and instrument both of a very closely knit union with God and of the unity of the whole human race” (LG1). Pope Francis’ Encyclical *Fratelli Tutti* on Fraternity and Social Friendship (2020) advocates a social friendship rooted in universal fraternity based on Christian love as an alternative to false universalism of globalization (FT 99-100).

Conclusion

The mission of the Church today is to proclaim and embody Christ as the restorer of humanity, the reconciler of communities, and the light for all nations. Evangelization is not a mere pastoral technique or institutional function; it is the Church’s participation in the *missio Dei*, the divine work of redeeming humanity and renewing creation in Christ through the Spirit. At its core lies the restoration of the *imago Dei*—the healing of fractured humanity, the renewal of the human vocation to reflect God’s glory, and the illumination of the world with divine light. To evangelize is to cooperate with God’s eschatological plan to bring forth the new man from the ruins of sin, personally, communally, and cosmically. This makes evangelization not only spiritually urgent but also anthropologically and socially indispensable in our age of fragmentation, anxiety, and dehumanization.

Gospel speaks not only of personal salvation but also of cultural transformation, social reconciliation, and the renewal of creation itself. In the contemporary world, where globalization, secularization, and cultural pluralism often obscure human dignity, the restored *imago Dei* provides a compelling framework for mission. It reminds us that

every person—regardless of gender, caste, creed, or ethnicity—bears the divine image, and that evangelization must include the healing of wounds inflicted by inequality, violence, and systemic injustice. Evangelization that integrates the anthropological implications of redemption becomes a counter-narrative to despair and opens a path toward authentic human flourishing, affirming dignity and fostering inclusion of every human person. By affirming the restoration of humanity’s true identity in Christ—the healing of the *imago Dei*—evangelization becomes the very service of healing, justice, and communion that our fractured world most desperately needs.

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